

Available online at [GSC Online Press Directory](https://www.gsconlinepress.com)

GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences

e-ISSN: 2581-3250, CODEN (USA): GBPSC2

Journal homepage: <https://www.gsconlinepress.com/journals/gscbps>

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Index of the phytoecological indicator species in the prevalent airborne pollen types in Akoko environment, Ondo State, Nigeria

Essien Benjamin Christopher ^{1,*} Idachaba Stephen Onojo ² and Okai Emmanuel Enemakwu ³¹ Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria.² Department of Integrated Science, Kogi State College of Education, Ankpa, Kogi State, Nigeria³ Department of Biological Sciences, Kogi State University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Publication history: Received on 14 August 2019; revised on 12 September 2019; accepted on 13 September 2019

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2019.8.3.0155>

Abstract

The study of vegetation and the way in which it has been altered and developed in the course of time indicates changes that have occurred in our terrestrial environment and is useful in providing vital information on environmental change, vegetation type, species composition and their utilization for sustainable development. This study was carried out in forty randomly selected locations so as to identify the different phytoecological indicator species and to also ascertain the present status of the vegetation of the catchment environment investigated. The airborne pollen grains were collected with Modified Tauber Sampler using simple random sampling technique and analyzed palynologically. Results showed 50,661 pollen grains counts comprising of 182 pollen types belonging to 74 angiospermic plant families were encountered. Three (3) of these pollen types were identified to family level, 57 to species level, 121 to generic level and one (1) unidentified. The pollen types identified in this study reflect to a large extent the phytoecological vegetation of the study area. Indicators of the Savanna taxa were the highest pollen contributors (55.74%) followed by Open forest taxa (22.72%), Human impact taxa (14.32%) and Lowland rainforest taxa (7.21%) respectively. About 44.19% of the plant sources identified are trees; the shrubs constitute about 25.96%, herbs 21.54%, herbaceous climbers 6.61%, lianas 1.10% and sedges 0.55%. The various ecological indicators species identified confirmed their origin as coming from the Forest-Savanna ecological zone that is anthropogenically disturbed. Such taxa could be properly conserved and their exploitation managed to prevent extinction thereby enhancing biodiversity sustainability.

Keywords: Airborne-pollen; Index; Indicator species; Phytoecology; Vegetation

1. Introduction

The vegetation of an area is an integral and basic component of the ecosystem and is sensitive to changes in the ecosystem. Consequently, vegetation changes are themselves a response to and a reflection of variation in one or more of the factors of the environment, particularly climate [1]. According to Sowunmi [2], a close relationship exists between vegetation and the rest of the environment, particularly climate and soil. Thus, the flora of an area provides a good reflection of the major climatic regime of the area. The influence of climate on other components of the environment is so great that every other climatic zone has its own characteristic vegetation type.

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: benjaminessien8@gmail.com

Plants are therefore among the best indicators of the environment especially of the climate, soil and fauna [3]. Certain individual or assemblages of plants are known to be characteristics of specific ecological zone and the occurrence of the fossils of such ecological indicator species in sediments is considered a reflection of contemporary ecological conditions. For example, the tropical rainforest is characterized by broad-leaved species, the savanna characterized by grasses, the desert by ephemeral and sclerophyllous plants and the cold regions of the world characterized by evergreen conifers [4].

The study of vegetation and the way in which it has been altered and developed in the course of time indicates past changes that have occurred in our terrestrial environment. Variations in climate and in the intensity of human activities in historic and prehistoric times have made their mark upon vegetation, and the plants themselves have left a record of these changes in the form of vast quantities of pollen grains which have survived in contemporary sediments [5]. The most common plant remains in Quaternary deposits are the pollen grains of flowering plants (Spermatophyte) and the spores of ferns (Pteridophyte) or mosses (Bryophytes); all of which are not visible to the naked eyes. The examination of pollen grains and spores do not only provide qualitative information on the plant present, but also quantitative information on their abundance. Thus, conclusion can be drawn about former vegetation conditions [6].

The relevance of atmospheric pollen content to the vegetation of a region is related to the palynomorphs produced *in situ* and those supplied from the surrounding zones [7-8]. Pollen and spores are generally produced in excess of the biological needs of the plants. Established observations have shown that anemophilous plants release large quantities of pollen into the air, while entomophilous taxa release smaller amounts. The behavioral patterns leads to differences in the quantity of pollen and spores of various taxa available in the atmosphere, and which of them can be trapped during sampling [9].

Germeraad *et al.* [10] and Traverse [11] in Ige [12] reported that there has been no significant change in the floras at the family and generic levels, since the Miocene in tropical low latitudes, including the Niger Delta (of Southern Nigeria where Akoko environment is a part). Rymer [13] and Birks and Birks [14] reported that the relationships between plants and climates have not changed with time at least from the time period of the Neogene. Several investigations for example, [15-19] have demonstrated that characteristics pollen assemblages are associated with regions of distinct vegetation. Thus, pollen-producing plants that are characteristic of or adapted morphologically and physiologically to specific ecological conditions and which have a restricted distribution are among the best indicators of their depositional environments.

Interpretation of pollen assemblages are based on empirically determined relationship between modern pollen and modern vegetation. Correspondence between pollen assemblage types and vegetation has been found in all parts of the world. It can be shown on one site that the percentages of pollen are unequal to the percentages of plants in the vegetation. This is largely because there are differences in the amounts of pollen produced by different species. There are also differences in the case with which pollen grains of different types are dispersed by the wind, differences in resistance to decay, and so forth [4].

Consequently, the nature of the vegetation cannot be deduced intuitively, from the frequencies of pollen in the assemblage. This is so even though geographic trends in modern pollen percentages are often similar (although not precisely parallel) to the trends in the abundance of species in the vegetation. But despite the lack of a simple one-to-one correlation between pollen and plant frequencies, the pollen in the sediments is uniquely related to the frequencies of plants [1], [5]. Some plants inhabiting specific environments tend to become genetically adapted to the environmental conditions such that they become more predominant than others [20]. They are generally the most conspicuous and may be indicator of a particular ecological zone and may also be used as standard in identifying similar communities elsewhere [3]. This study is aimed at identifying the phytoecological indicator species and to determine the present status of the vegetation of the catchment environment investigated. The results of this study are anticipated to provide useful information on the conservation and sustainable exploitation of these indicator species through appropriate biotechnological measures.

2. Material and methods

Forty locations were randomly selected within the four Local Government Areas of Akoko division, Ondo State, Nigeria as sampling sites. The sampling sites for the study were purposely selected to reflect as far as possible the Local Government Area of the study. In choosing the sites, consideration was also given to urbanization, accessibility, and safety of the sampling (experimental materials) instruments among others [21].

At each site, a pollen trap (Modified Tauber Sampler) was mounted according to the methods of Tauber [22, 23], Pardoe *et al.* [24] and Giesecke *et al.* [25]. Prior to this, a mixture of glycerol (65 ml), formalin (30 ml) and phenol (5 ml) was poured into each of the trap. The positions of the traps at various locations were recorded using a Global Position System (GPS). The solutions in the trap prevented the palynomorphs from drying up, kill insects and also prevented the decay of dead organisms. The trap was left to stand throughout the duration of the study period. Fortnightly of each month, solution collection was done. The traps were washed with water to remove any contaminants and were then recharged with the above mentioned chemical solutions. This procedure was repeated bi-monthly from October 2016 to December 2017 (dry season and rainy seasons' samples) for one year. The palynomorphs were recovered through centrifugation at 2000 r.p.m (revolution per minute) for 5 minutes and supernatant decanted each time. The precipitates were washed twice with distilled water and recovered through centrifugation. The sediments were treated with glacial acetic acid to remove water before acetolysis [26, 27]. The recovered precipitates were washed with glacial acetic acid, and finally washed twice with distilled water, centrifuged each time and decanted. The recovered palynomorphs were stored in a plastic vials in glycerin and ethanol solution (2:1).

The palynomorphs were analysed palynologically and microscopically with Olympus microscope at x400 magnification for counting and Leica microscope at x1000 magnification for detailed morphological studies. Palynomorphs identification, counting and classification were done with the help of reference descriptions and photomicrographs from Agwu and Akanbi [27], Bonnefille and Rioulet [28], Sowunmi [29] and Shubharani *et al.* [30]. In addition, prepared slides of pollen samples in the Palynological Research Unit; Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba- Akoko, Nigeria were used.

3. Results and discussion

A total of 182 pollen types were identified across the study locations. These pollen types belong to 74 angiospermic plant families (Table 1). Out of these 74 plant families encountered, 66 families belong to the dicotyledonous plants, 6 to monocotyledonous plants, and 1 was unidentified (Indeterminata). Photomicrographs of pollen grains of some selected indicator species are shown in Figure 1.

Generally, the pollen types identified in this study reflected to a large extent the phytoecological vegetation of the study area. Some of the pollen types identified reflected plant species of different ecological indicators based on the classification of White [31] and Agwu [8]. Absolute pollen counts for the phytoecological indicator species across the study period is presented in Table 1. Statistical analysis using Duncan Multiple Range Test showed that there was significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the Mean pollen grains abundance classified based on phytoecological indicator species. Indicators of the Savanna taxa were the highest pollen contributors (55.74%) followed by Open forest taxa (22.72%), Human impact taxa (14.32%) and Lowland rainforest taxa (7.21%) respectively (Table 2). The various phytoecological indicators species identified confirmed their origin as coming from the Forest- Savanna ecological zone that is anthropogenically disturbed.

3.1. Lowland rainforest taxa

Absolute pollen counts for the phytoecological indicator species across the study period showed that a total of 3,651 pollen grains were counted for Lowland Rainforest taxa with a percentage composition of 7.21% (Table 1). Analysis of variance showed that the Mean pollen grains abundance recorded for these taxa is 0.39 ± 0.02^a (Table 2). The characteristic plants in this group include *Aneilema* sp., *Bombax buonopozense*, *Berlinia grandiflora*, *Bidens pilosa*, *Brachystegia eurycoma*, *Canarium schweinforthii*, *Ceiba pentandra*, *Celtis* sp., *Cola* sp., *Combretum* sp., *Costus afer*, *Dissotis* sp., *Eugenia* sp., *Garcinia kola*, *Gardenia* sp., *Gentianella amarella*, *Lapisanthes senegalensis*, *Lophira alata*, *Mallotus subulatus*, *Merremia* sp., *Microdesmis* sp., *Milicia excelsa*, *Morus* sp., *Musanga cercropioides*, *Nesogordonia papaverifera*, *Parinari curatellifolia*, *Paullinia pinnata*, *Pentaclethra macrophylla*, *Sapium* sp., *Spondias mombin*, *Sterculia* sp., *Symphonia globulifera*, *Talinum triangulare*, *Tessmania* sp., *Treulia africana*, *Trema guineense* and *Triplochiton scleroxylon* etc.

Table 1: Absolute monthly pollen grains counts for the phyto-ecological indicator species across the study period

Pollen type / Month	Plant Form	Plant Family	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	Jun.	Jul.	Aug.	Sep.	Total
LOWLAND RAINFOREST TAXA															
<i>Aneilema</i> sp.	Herb	Commelinaceae	0	0	0	0	0	3	7	0	0	0	0	0	10
<i>Berlinia grandifolia</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	0	8	5	21	0	4	18	0	0	0	0	0	56
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	Herb	Asteraceae	5	21	11	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	49
<i>Bombax buonopozense</i>	Tree	Bombacaceae	17	11	6	3	4	0	12	17	13	0	3	25	111
<i>Brachystegia eurycoma</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	0	0	0	0	0	22	5	1	0	0	0	0	28
<i>Canarium schweinforthii</i>	Tree	Burseraceae	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	7	0	0	1	12
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	Tree	Bombacaceae	0	3	0	2	0	2	7	1	0	0	0	0	15
<i>Celtis</i> sp.	Tree	Cannabaceae	1	0	0	15	0	7	3	1	0	0	2	0	29
<i>Cola</i> sp.	Tree	Sterculiaceae	6	0	9	24	10	25	15	11	13	10	8	4	135
<i>Combretum</i> sp.	Shrub	Combretaceae	35	42	30	24	47	40	31	42	42	12	20	11	376
<i>Costus afer</i>	Herb	Costaceae	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	3	2	5	0	0	13
<i>Dissotis</i> sp.	Shrub	Melastomataceae	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	26	21	41	112
<i>Euginea</i> sp.	Shrub	Myrtaceae	16	61	0	1	3	1	27	94	13	10	41	57	324
<i>Garcinia kola</i>	Tree	Clusiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	25	29	0	4	61
<i>Gardenia</i> sp.	Tree	Rubiaceae	2	5	7	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23
<i>Gentianella amerella</i>	Herb	Gentianaceae	0	1	2	3	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	10
<i>Lepisanthes senegalensis</i>	Shrub	Diptilomiodeae	0	0	0	0	0	6	9	0	0	0	0	0	15
<i>Lophira alata</i>	Tree	Ochnaceae	4	9	41	6	10	15	14	14	2	0	4	4	123
<i>Mallotus subulatus</i>	Shrub	Euphorbiaceae	0	0	0	0	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	6

<i>Merremia</i> sp.	H/ Climber	Convolvulaceae	4	2	0	0	0	6	0	0	12	0	0	0	24
<i>Microdesmis</i> sp.	Shrub	Pandaceae	2	5	13	11	0	36	21	10	0	0	1	1	100
<i>Milicia excelsa</i>	Tree	Moraceae	19	49	141	160	0	253	6	12	5	0	0	0	645
<i>Morus</i> sp.	Shrub	Moraceae	0	0	0	0	0	10	4	0	0	0	0	0	14
<i>Musanga cercropioides</i>	Tree	Urticaceae	7	21	10	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	3	57
<i>Nesogordonia papaverifera</i>	Tree	Malvaceae	9	0	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	41
<i>Parinari curatellifolia</i>	Tree	Chrysobalanaceae	0	0	0	0	0	31	5	11	9	0	0	0	56
<i>Paullinia pinnata</i>	H/ Climber	Sapindaceae	0	0	0	1	3	0	11	36	21	0	0	2	74
<i>Pentaclethra macrophylla</i>	Tree	Mimosoideae	0	0	0	0	19	37	25	11	21	32	0	15	160
<i>Sapium</i> sp.	Shrub	Euphorbiaceae	3	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
<i>Spondias mombin</i>	Tree	Anacardiaceae	0	2	0	2	0	1	2	0	2	0	0	1	10
<i>Sterculia</i> sp.	Tree	Sterculiaceae	8	27	12	16	11	5	2	3	5	5	8	10	112
<i>Symphonia globulifera</i>	Tree	Clusiaceae	2	2	5	0	0	8	12	5	0	0	0	0	34
<i>Talinum triangulare</i>	Herb	Portulacaceae	5	12	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	18	48
<i>Tessmania</i> sp.	Herb	Caesalpinoideae	11	5	3	0	0	3	7	0	0	0	0	0	29
<i>Treculia africana</i>	Tree	Moraceae	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
<i>Trema guineense</i>	Tree	Urticaceae	5	4	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	12	44
<i>Triplochiton scleroxylon</i>	Tree	Sterculiaceae	131	102	23	93	18	20	40	229	8	7	7	2	680
SUB TOTAL			306	394	364	414	131	542	289	501	213	138	134	225	3,651
% COMPOSITION															7.21%
OPEN FOREST TAXA															

<i>Afzelia africana</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	6	0	0	0	0	10
<i>Albizia</i> sp.	Tree	Mimosoideae	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	24	2	6	25	54	116
<i>Albizia zygia</i>	Tree	Mimosoideae	0	191	151	177	33	0	0	0	13	17	0	0	582
<i>Alchornea cordifolia</i>	Shrub	Euphorbiaceae	65	847	497	196	99	202	99	56	29	7	14	15	2126
<i>Allophyllus africanus</i>	Shrub	Sapindaceae	4	0	5	6	4	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	23
<i>Alstonia boonei</i>	Tree	Apocynaceae	0	0	0	0	0	8	2	1	2	2	0	1	16
<i>Anisotes</i> sp.	Shrub	Acanthaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2	1	0	0	8
<i>Anthocleista djalonensis</i>	Tree	Loganiaceae	0	0	13	3	3	2	2	5	2	1	0	0	31
<i>Baphia</i> sp.	Shrub	Papilionoideae	1	0	0	0	0	11	9	2	0	0	0	0	23
<i>Blighia unijugata</i>	Tree	Sapindaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	11	3	0	0	0	19
<i>Canthium</i> sp.	Tree	Rubiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	3	7	16	31
<i>Cnestis ferruginea</i>	Shrub	Connaraceae	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	11	0	0	0	0	16
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Tree	Arecaceae	0	0	5	2	5	15	5	10	2	0	0	0	44
<i>Commiphora africana</i>	Tree	Burseraceae	0	12	10	0	0	7	19	38	0	0	0	0	86
<i>Croton</i> sp.	Herb	Euphorbiaceae	0	0	2	4	0	9	3	0	0	0	0	0	18
<i>Dalbergia</i> sp.	Tree	Papilionoideae	0	4	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
<i>Dichapetalum</i> sp.	Shrub	Dichapetalaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	0	5
<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	Tree	Arecaceae	379	1411	1148	395	247	622	594	320	146	123	187	350	5922
<i>Ficus exasperate</i>	Tree	Moraceae	0	1	2	1	0	9	7	0	0	0	0	0	20
<i>Gaertnera paniculata</i>	Shrub	Rubiaceae	5	22	9	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	46
<i>Gutenbergia</i> sp.	Herb	Asteraceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	28	54	552	4	1	3	642
<i>Harungana madagascariensis</i>	Tree	Hypericaceae	0	0	0	2	8	5	21	20	25	27	31	35	174
<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	Tree	Irvingiaceae	7	7	4	123	15	202	29	31	2	3	3	0	426

<i>Kedrostis africana</i>	H/ Climber	Cucurbitaceae	0	0	0	0	0	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	8
<i>Kigelia africana</i>	Tree	Bignoniaceae	8	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	25
<i>Lasiodiscus</i> sp.	Tree	Rhamnaceae	0	1	2	1	0	9	7	0	0	0	0	0	20
<i>Motandra</i> sp.	Lianas	Apocynaceae	3	0	0	0	0	3	5	7	0	0	0	2	20
<i>Newbouldia laevis</i>	Shrub	Bigniniaceae	0	31	19	0	0	41	0	13	8	11	0	0	123
<i>Periploaca</i> sp.	Shrub	Apocynaceae	4	283	0	224	12	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	524
<i>Pinus caribaea</i>	Tree	Pinaceae	2	7	0	4	0	1	4	4	1	2	5	9	39
<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Herb	Plumbaginaceae	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	11	21
<i>Pterocarpus osum</i>	Tree	Papilionoideae	0	3	2	0	3	1	3	0	2	0	0	0	14
<i>Pycnanthus angolensis</i>	Tree	Myristicaceae	10	61	21	32	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	124
<i>Raphia</i> sp.	Tree	Areaceae	0	0	0	3	6	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	12
<i>Securinega virosa</i>	Shrub	Phyllanthaceae	8	27	12	16	11	5	2	3	5	5	8	10	112
<i>Solenostemon monostacyus</i>	Herb	Lamiaceae	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	9
<i>Uapaca</i> sp.	Tree	Phyllanthaceae	0	1	0	0	0	0	8	0	26	2	5	1	43
<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	Shrub	Asteraceae	2	7	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	16
SUB TOTAL			505	2916	1926	1199	452	1169	868	623	825	214	291	515	11,503
% COMPOSITION															22.72%
SAVANNA TAXA															
<i>Acacia senegal</i>	Shrub	Mimosoideae	0	3	8	0	0	7	14	5	0	0	0	0	37
<i>Acacia</i> sp.	Shrub	Mimosoideae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	3
<i>Acalypha</i> sp.	Herb	Euphorbiaceae	0	4	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15
<i>Annona senegalensis</i>	Tree	Annonaceae	0	0	2	3	0	3	15	0	0	8	3	0	34
<i>Anthrocaryon micraster</i>	Tree	Anacardiaceae	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	6

<i>Aubrevillea kerstingii</i>	Tree	Mimosoideae	16	11	6	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	48
<i>Barteria nigritiana</i>	Shrub	Passifloraceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	2	0	0	0	7
<i>Blepharis</i> sp.	Herb	Acanthaceae	5	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	11
<i>Borreria</i> sp.	Herb	Rubiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	10	4	0	0	0	0	0	14
<i>Bridellia ferruginea</i>	Shrub	Phyllanthaceae	2	0	5	0	0	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	13
<i>Cochlospermum planchonii</i>	Shrub	Cochlospermaceae	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	30	1	0	0	36
<i>Crossopteryx febrifuga</i>	Tree	Rubiaceae	3	34	5	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	55
Cyperaceae	Sedges	Cyperaceae	26	13	12	10	9	17	10	116	42	25	22	19	321
<i>Daniellia oliveri</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	14	11	19	0	5	9	1	8	0	0	25	34	126
<i>Deterium macrocarpum</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	12	7	0	22
<i>Dialium guineense</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	38	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	41	18	100
<i>Diospyros mespiliformis</i>	Tree	Ebenaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	10	88	237	0	338
<i>Diospyros</i> sp.	Tree	Ebenaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	8	0	0	0	14
<i>Fillipendula ulmaria</i>	Herb	Rosaceae	14	11	3	8	0	48	22	159	12	4	12	7	300
<i>Gloriosa superba</i>	H/ Climber	Colchicaceae	0	0	0	0	0	5	7	4	2	0	3	0	21
<i>Hymenocardia acida</i>	Shrub	Phyllanthaceae	6	30	8	78	18	20	40	229	8	7	7	2	453
<i>Hypoestes</i> sp.	Herb	Acanthaceae	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
<i>Indigofera</i> sp.	Herb	Papilionoideae	0	8	0	0	0	12	3	7	11	0	0	0	41
<i>Khaya ivorensis</i>	Tree	Meliaceae	4	2	7	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16
<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Tree	Meliaceae	1	15	2	7	7	23	63	9	1	8	9	4	149
<i>Knautia</i> sp.	Herb	Caprifoliaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2	3	10
<i>Lannea acida</i>	Tree	Anacardiaceae	195	121	231	0	0	91	181	71	0	33	51	0	974
<i>Leucas</i> sp.	Herb	Lamiaceae	7	7	9	2	1	0	0	0	2	9	16	5	58

<i>Linum catharticum</i>	Herb	Linaceae	0	0	0	2	2	7	5	3	10	18	0	0	47
<i>Linum</i> sp.	Herb	Linaceae	0	0	0	1	3	1	1	9	2	5	8	12	42
<i>Maytenus</i> sp.	Shrub	Celastraceae	0	0	0	4	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13
<i>Mimosa pigra</i>	Tree	Mimosoideae	0	0	0	19	11	0	121	53	28	0	0	0	232
<i>Morelia senegalensis</i>	Shrub	Rubiaceae	19	49	141	160	0	253	6	12	5	0	0	0	645
<i>Nauclea latifolia</i>	Tree	Rubiaceae	16	1	0	1	5	27	61	94	16	10	41	57	329
<i>Olax subcorpioidea</i>	Tree	Olacaceae	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	6
<i>Olax</i> sp.	Tree	Olacaceae	4	0	5	6	4	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	23
<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Tree	Mimosoideae	78	137	225	39	18	0	11	182	14	5	4	15	728
<i>Phyllanthus</i> sp.	Herb	Phyllanthaceae	6	0	9	24	10	25	15	11	13	10	8	4	135
<i>Platostoma africanum</i>	Herb	Lamiaceae	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	11
<i>Piliostigma thonningii</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	12	26
Poaceae	Herb	Poaceae	3418	3892	4145	1679	594	551	567	889	699	703	565	3109	20811
<i>Prosopis africana</i>	Tree	Mimosoideae	0	0	0	215	291	131	0	0	0	0	0	0	637
<i>Rauvolfia vomitoria</i>	Shrub	Apocynaceae	0	0	0	0	14	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	23
<i>Rhynchosia</i> sp.	Herb	Papilionoideae	0	0	0	0	0	5	4	3	0	0	0	0	12
<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	Herb	Pedaliaceae	125	72	15	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	227
<i>Sida acuta</i>	Shrub	Malvaceae	12	308	18	49	162	2	9	3	19	1	34	24	641
<i>Syzygium guineense</i>	Tree	Myrtaceae	14	11	3	8	0	48	22	159	12	4	12	7	300
<i>Trichilia prieureana</i>	Tree	Meliaceae	0	3	3	0	0	3	7	0	0	0	2	0	18
<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i>	Tree	Sapotaceae	2	5	11	7	0	27	18	10	0	0	1	1	82
SUB TOTAL			4030	4764	4904	2365	1169	1343	1213	2049	949	963	1116	3353	28,218
% COMPOSITION															55.74%
HUMAN IMPACT															

TAXA															
<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i>	Herb	Malvaceae	9	0	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30
<i>Adenanthera pavonina</i>	Tree	Mimosoideae	0	0	0	0	0	2	6	2	1	0	0	0	11
Amaranthaceae/ Chenopiaceae	Herb	Amaranthaceae/ Chenopodiaceae	26	28	24	16	11	158	35	53	26	9	3	26	415
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	Tree	Anacardiaceae	0	6	4	2	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	24
<i>Antidesma</i> sp.	Shrub	Phyllanthaceae	14	3	401	4	2	8	2	2	7	4	0	27	474
<i>Aspilia africana</i>	Herb	Asteraceae	77	446	31	66	18	10	4	17	20	39	104	415	1247
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Tree	Meliaceae	2	2	9	0	0	5	6	1	7	5	6	0	43
<i>Calycobolus</i> sp.	H/ Climber	Convolvulaceae	0	0	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
<i>Capparis</i> sp.	Shrub	Capparaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	6
<i>Carica papaya</i>	Herb	Caricaceae	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	42
<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>	Tree	Casuarinaceae	33	14	23	27	17	61	31	110	34	33	90	719	1192
<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Tree	Rutaceae	4	7	35	6	10	12	14	9	2	0	4	4	107
<i>Cleome</i> sp.	Herb	Capparaceae	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	1	9
<i>Corchorus olitorius</i>	Herb	Malvaceae	0	3	0	0	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
<i>Cucumis</i> sp.	H/ Climber	Cucurbitaceae	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	6
<i>Delonix regia</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	0	17	0	2	0	0	23	6	0	10	1	3	62
<i>Dioscorea</i> sp.	Lianas	Dioscoreaceae	2	0	0	0	0	8	3	1	0	0	0	0	14
<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	Herb	Asteraceae	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
<i>Empetrum nigrum</i>	Shrub	Caesalpinoideae	0	14	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	26
<i>Eucalyptus globus</i>	Tree	Myrtaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	7	16	26
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Herb	Euphorbiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	12	17	82	33	0	0	8	152
<i>Euphorbia</i> sp.	Herb	Euphorbiaceae	0	0	1	0	1	3	3	0	1	0	0	0	9

<i>Fagus</i> sp.	Tree	Fagaceae	0	4	1	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Tree	Verbenaceae	3	8	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8	24
<i>Heliotropium</i> sp.	Herb	Boraginaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	3
<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i>	Herb	Lamiaceae	205	47	76	24	6	27	9	10	4	1	0	12	421
<i>Ipomoea</i> sp.	H/ Climber	Convolvulaceae	0	4	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	Shrub	Euphorbiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	2	2	2	14
<i>Justicia</i> sp.	Herb	Acanthaceae	0	5	0	0	0	4	1	3	4	1	2	1	21
<i>Leea guineensis</i>	Shrub	Leeaceae	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	5
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	3	21	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29
<i>Linnaea borealis</i>	Shrub	Caprifoliaceae	0	5	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
<i>Luffa cylindrical</i>	H/ Climber	Cucurbitaceae	5	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	10
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Tree	Anacardiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	3	0	0	0	0	12
<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Shrub	Euphorbiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	4	1	0	0	0	8
<i>Ocimum</i> sp.	Shrub	Lamiaceae	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	5	18	71	128
<i>Physalis angulata</i>	Herb	Solanaceae	0	1	0	0	0	0	8	0	26	2	5	1	43
<i>Protea elliotii</i>	Shrub	Proteaceae	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	6
<i>Protea madiensis</i>	Shrub	Proteaceae	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Shrub	Myrtaceae	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	5
<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Shrub	Euphorbiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	6	3	0	0	0	17
<i>Senna occidentale</i>	Tree	Caesalpinoideae	181	59	101	61	68	12	35	28	16	6	14	45	626
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Shrub	Solanaceae	14	3	401	4	2	8	2	2	7	4	0	27	474
<i>Solanum torvum</i>	Shrub	Solanaceae	2	0	5	0	0	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	13
<i>Spigelia anthelmia</i>	Herb	Loganiaceae	2	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	12
<i>Stachytarpheta</i> sp.	Shrub	Verbenaceae	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	6

<i>Stereospermum kunthianum</i>	Tree	Bignoniaceae	0	7	3	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24
<i>Tecoma stans</i>	Shrub	Bignoniaceae	0	3	5	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	Tree	Verbenaceae	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
<i>Tetracera</i> sp.	H/ Climber	Dilleniaceae	0	3	0	0	0	1	2	4	0	0	0	0	10
<i>Tieghemella africana</i>	Tree	Urticaceae	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	11	21
<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Herb	Asteraceae	68	478	19	85	11	5	9	9	11	42	100	255	1092
<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	H/ Climber	Papilionoideae	5	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	25
<i>Vitex doniana</i>	Tree	Lamiaceae	21	2	6	2	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	63
<i>Vitex grandifolia</i>	Tree	Lamiaceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	26	44	0	0	72
<i>Polygala</i> sp.	H/ Climber	Polygalaceae	10	21	15	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	5	77
<i>Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides</i>	Tree	Rutaceae	0	2	6	0	0	3	0	5	0	0	0	0	16
SUB TOTAL			755	1221	1215	364	187	351	254	380	237	210	382	1694	7,250
% COMPOSITION															14.32%
INDETERMINATA			1	2	7	1	6	1	4	4	1	5	3	4	39
GRAND TOTAL			5597	9297	8416	4343	1945	3406	2628	3557	2225	1530	1926	5791	50,661

H/Climber = Herbaceous Climber

Figure 1 Photomicrograph of pollen grains of some selected indicator species

Table 2 Mean pollen grains abundance classified based on phytoecological indicator species

S/N	Phytoecological Group	Mean Pollen count±S.E
1	Savanna Taxa	2.39±0.16 ^c
2	Open Forest Taxa	1.29±0.08 ^b
3	Human Impact Taxa	0.54±0.05 ^a
4	Lowland Rainforest Taxa	0.39±0.02 ^a
	p Value	0.000*

Means not followed by the same letter are significantly different at P<0.05 (DMRT).

* - significant at p<0.05

Table 3 Mean pollen grains abundance classified based on plant form

S/N	Plant Form	Mean Pollen count±S.E
1	Herbs	44.02±3.47 ^c
2	Shrubs	2.87±1.26 ^b
3	Trees	0.86±0.36 ^a
4	Sedges	0.48±0.39 ^a
5	Herbaceous climber	0.16±0.03 ^a
6	Lianas	0.07±0.02 ^a
	p Value	0.000*

Means not followed by the same letter are significantly different at P<0.05 (DMRT).

* - significant at p<0.05.

Table 4 Percentage composition of pollen grains abundance classified based on plant form

S/N	Plant Form	No of Species present	No of Pollen counted	% Composition
1.	Herbs	41	26,078	51.47
2.	Trees	82	16,813	33.18
3.	Shrubs	45	7,109	14.03
4.	Sedges	1	321	0.63
5.	Herbaceous climbers	11	266	0.52
6.	Lianas	2	34	0.06
	Grand Total	182	50661	99.89

3.2. Open forest taxa

These taxa contributed 11,503 pollen grains with percentage abundance of 22.72% in terms of absolute pollen count classified based on the phytoecological indicator species (Table 1). Statistical analysis using Duncan Multiple Range Test showed that the Mean pollen grains abundance of 1.29 ± 0.08^b was documented for this group (Table 2). The characteristic plants in this group include *Afzelia africana*, *Albizia* sp., *Albizia zygia*, *Alchornea cordifolia*, *Allophyllus africanus*, *Alstonia boonei*, *Anisotes* sp., *Anthocleista djalensis*, *Baphia* sp., *Blighia unijugata*, *Canthium* sp., *Cnestis ferruginea*, *Cocos nucifera*, *Commiphora africana*, *Croton* sp., *Dalbergia* sp., *Dichapetalum* sp., *Elaeis guineensis*, *Ficus exaspinata*, *Gaertnera paniculata*, *Gutenbergia* sp., *Harungana madagascariensis*, *Irvingia gabonensis*, *Kedrostis africana*, *Kigelia africana*, *Lasiodiscus* sp., *Motandra* sp., *Newbouldia leavis*, *Periploca* sp., *Pinus caribaea*, *Plumbago zeylanica*, *Pterocarpus osum*, *Pycnanthus angolensis*, *Raphia* sp., *Securinega virosa*, *Solenostemon monostacyus*, *Uapaca* sp., and *Vernonia amygdalina* etc.

3.3. Savanna taxa

In terms of absolute pollen counts for the phytoecological indicator species across the study period, some Savanna indicator species were also identified in the samples and results showed that these taxa were the largest pollen contributor. A total of 28,218 pollen grains were counted for these taxa with a percentage composition of 55.74% (Table 1). Duncan Multiple Range Test showed that the Mean pollen grains abundance of 2.39 ± 0.16^c was documented for this group (Table 2). The species in these taxa includes the Families Cyperaceae and Poaceae as well as *Acacia senegalensis*, *Acacia* sp., *Acalypha* sp., *Annona senegalensis*, *Anthrocaryon micraster*, *Aubrevillea kerstingii*, *Barteria nigritiana*, *Blepharis* sp., *Borreria* sp., *Bridelia ferruginea*, *Cochlospermum planchonii*, *Crossopteryx febrifuga*, *Daniellia oliveri*, *Deterium macrocarpum*, *Dialium guineense*, *Diospyros mespiliformis*, *Diospyros* sp., *Fillipendula ulmaria*, *Gloriosa superba*, *Hymenocardia acida*, *Hypoestes* sp., *Indigofera* sp., *Khaya ivorensis*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Knautia* sp., *Lannea acida*, *Leucas* sp., *Linum catharticum*, *Limum* sp., *Maytenus* sp., *Mimosa pigra*, *Morelia senegalensis*, *Nauclea latifolia*, *Olax subcorpioides*, *Olax* sp., *Parkia biglobosa*, *Phyllanthus* sp., *Platostoma africana*, *Piliostigma thonningii*, *Prosopis africana*, *Rauvolfia vomitoria*, *Rhynchosia* sp., *Sesamum indicum*, *Sida acuta*, *Syzygium guineense*, *Trichilia prieureana* and *Vitellaria paradoxa*.

3.4. Human impact taxa

The results of this study showed that numerous bioparticles indicative of human impact taxa were documented. Absolute counts of 7,250 pollen grains with percentage composition of 14.32% were documented for these taxa (Table 1). Statistical analysis using Duncan Multiple Range Test showed that the Mean pollen grains abundance of 0.54 ± 0.05^a was documented for this group (Table 2). These taxa include pollen types of plant species associated with horticulture and agricultural activities such as *Abelmoschus esculentus*, *Adenantha pavonina*, *Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae*, *Anacardium occidentale*, *Antidesma* sp., *Aspilia africana*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Calycobolus* sp., *Capparis* sp., *Carica papaya*, *Casuarina equisetifolia*, *Citrus* sp., *Cleome* sp., *Corchorus olitorius*, *Cucumis* sp., *Delonix regia*, *Dioscorea* sp., *Emilia sonchifolia*, *Empetrum nigrum*, *Eucalyptus globus*, *Euphorbia hirta*, *Euphorbia* sp., *Fagus* sp., *Gmelina arborea*, *Heliotropium* sp., *Hyptis suaveolens*, *Ipomoea* sp., *Jatropha curcus*, *Justicia* sp., *Leea guineensis*, *Leuceana leucocephalus*, *Linnaea borealis*, *Luffa cylindrica*, *Mangifera indica*, *Manihot esculenta*, *Ocimum* sp., *Physalis angulata*, *Pinus caribaea*, *Protea elliotii*, *Protea madiensis*, *Psidium guajava*, *Ricinus communis*, *Senna occidentale*, *Solanum melongena*, *Solanum torvum*, *Spigelia anthelmia*, *Stachytarpheta* sp., *Stereospermum kunthianum*, *Tecoma stans*, *Tectona grandis*, *Tetracera* sp., *Tieghemella africana*, *Tridax procumbens*, *Vigna unguiculata*, *Vitex doniana*, *Vitex grandifolia*, *Polygala* sp., and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*.

For most of these indicator species, their pollen grains were recorded sporadically where they appeared in some of the study locations, while the pollen of such plants as *Azadirachta indica*, *Casuarina equisetifolia*, *Hyptis suaveolens*, and the members of the families Asteraceae and *Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae* were recorded in more than 10 locations.

Moreso, the pollen of some taxa such as *Aspilia africana*, *Nauclea latifolia*, *Sida acuta* and the Family Poaceae were documented in all the study locations. Also, other indicators of human impact/ activities included charred plant particles and diatom frustules.

3.5. Plant form

With respect to plant forms (habits), six groups of plants: trees, shrubs, herbs, lianas, sedges, and herbaceous climbers contributed greatly to the total pollen rain. About 44.19% of the plant sources identified are trees; the shrubs constitute about 25.96%, herbs 21.54%, herbaceous climbers 6.61%, lianas 1.10% and sedges 0.55%. The quantity of pollen contributed by each of these groups varied considerably. Herbs contributed the highest percentage of pollen

concentration (51.47%) in the pollen record followed by trees (33.18%), shrubs (14.03%), sedges (0.63), herbaceous climbers (0.52%) and lianas (0.06%). The percentage contributions are in terms of the pollen contributed by the constituent species of each plant group. The Mean quantity of pollen grains classified based on Plant Form is shown in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

3.6. Relationship between airborne pollen grains assemblage and vegetation

The airborne pollen assemblage trapped in this study generally reflects the regional vegetation of the catchment area which depicts tropical rainforest type (Tables 1). The pollen types recorded in this study represent the subtype vegetation of the study area which includes tropical rainforest, closed/ open forest, riparian forest, woodland shrub grasslands, and human impact ecological zones. The floristic composition of these subtype vegetations are subsumed into three major phytoecological groups upon which other small localized subtype vegetations are represented. These are (i) the tropical rainforest, closed/open forest species represented by pollen of *Elaeis guineensis*, Cyperaceae, Moraceae, *Senna occidentalis*, *Alchornea cordifolia*, *Bombax buonopozense*, *Irvingia gabonensis*, *Anthocleista djalonensis*, *Canarium schweinfurthii*, *Musanga cecropiodes*, *Pentaclethra macrophylla* and *Pycnanthus angolensis* among others; (ii) the woodland shrub components represented by pollen grains of Poaceae, *Azelia africana*, *Berlinia grandifolia*, *Combretum* sp., *Crossopteryx febrifuga*, *Daniellia oliveri*, *Dissotis* sp., *Euginea* sp., *Gloriosa superba*, *Hymenocardia acida*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Lannea acida*, *Lophira alata*, *Nauclea latifolia*, *Parkia biglobosa*, *Phyllanthus* sp., *Prosopis africana*, *Protea* sp., *Rauvolfia vomitoria*, *Syzygium guineense*, and *Uapaca* sp. among others; (iii) the human impact species represented by pollen of exotic plants that serves aesthetic, economic and agricultural purposes as well as other related functions. They include *Abelmoschus esculentus*, Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae, *Anacardium occidentale*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Carica papaya*, *Casuarina equisetifolia*, *Cocos nucifera*, *Cola* sp., *Delonix regia*, *Dioscorea* sp., *Gmelina arborea*, *Jatropha* sp., *Justicia* sp., *Luffa cylindrica*, *Mangifera indica*, *Manihot esculenta*, *Mimosa pigra*, *Pentaclethra macrophylla*, *Pinus caribaea*, *Ricinus communis*, *Sida acuta* and *Solanum melongena* among others. Most of these plants have been recorded in various studies in Nsukka (Enugu State); Aguata (Anambra State); Anyigba (Kogi State), Shomolu, Gbagada, Ayetoro-Itele (Lagos State) Nigeria [8, 27, 32, 33, 34, 35], [36, 37], [3, 38, 39, 40, 7], [41, 42]. The site to site variation in number of pollen types portrays not only the existence of subtype vegetations but also the floristic heterogeneity of the vegetation of the study area.

Of importance also is the presence of pollen types that are indicators of human impact such as those of horticulture (for example, in schools, health centres, streets, etc.), erosion control, etc. reflected evidence of agriculture and other anthropogenic activities. The impact of human on the vegetation has also resulted in the disappearance of some flora. Disappearance of some species is brought about by a combination of factors, including annual bush burning, excessive lumbering and firewood gathering, shifting cultivation and excessive grazing by livestock among others. As a result of these factors, the vegetation of the studied area has become impoverished with several economic species at the verge of extinction.

However, the result of the study was limited in terms of pollen-vegetation representation relationship. The first major reason is concerned with the differences in pollen production and dispersal among tropical plants in our study area [43, 44]. The entomophilous taxa are known to produce low quantities of pollen grains with poor dispersal quality and the anemophilous taxa are copious pollen producers with good aerodynamic qualities. This advantage makes the anemophilous plants to be well represented or even to be over-represented in pollen assemblage compared to the entomophilous taxa. A second possible explanation is the difficulty of identification of all pollen grains to the generic or specific level. For instance, some pollen types are identified only to family level such as Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae, Cyperaceae and Poaceae.

However, despite these limitations, the identified pollen grains so far still confirm the great floristic diversity and heterogeneity of the vegetation subtypes of the study area and the floristic heterogeneity in the study locations. Similar findings have been reported in South Congo [45], Nigeria [3, 4, 33, and 34] and Southern Cameroon [44].

4. Conclusion

The pollen types identified in this study reflect to a large extent the phytoecological vegetation of the studied environment. The presence of pollen types from exotic plants as part of the content of the atmospheric pollen content indicates clearly the impact of man on the environment. Pollen assemblages reflected tropical rainforest vegetation type despite high level of anthropogenic activities on the local vegetation. Most of these indicator species are at the verge of extinction through series of anthropogenic activities. Such flora could be properly conserved and their exploitation adequately managed through appropriate biotechnological interventions.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The corresponding author is grateful to the Almighty God for life, protection and inspirations; his wife Mrs. Glory Christopher Essien, and to the leadership of Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) for the monthly intervention given him during the period of this research.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Ige OE and Essien BC. (2019). The applications of pollen analysis in environmental monitoring in Akoko North-East Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 8(1), 64 - 77.
- [2] Sowunmi MA. (1987). Palynological studies in the Niger Delta. In: E.J. Alagoa, F.N. The early history of the Niger Delta. Helmat Buske Verlag Hamburg. 29-59.
- [3] Essien BC and Nkang AE. (2013). Evaluation of the phytoecological indicator species in the airborne palynomorphs from Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria. *Standard Scientific Research and Essays*, 1(14), 398- 402.
- [4] Essien BC. (2019). The study of Quaternary airborne palynomorphs in Akoko environment, Ondo State, Nigeria. PhD Thesis, Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba- Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria. 2 - 486.
- [5] Roberts N. (1998). The holocene: an environmental history. Basil-Blackwell, New York, 350- 361.
- [6] Overpeck JT. (1985). Quantitative interpretation of fossil spectra: dissimilarity coefficient and the methods of modern analogs. *Quaternary Research*, 23, 87-108.
- [7] Essien BC, Ige OE and Ekeyi D. (2016). Recent pollen rain in Anyigba: an indicator of the vegetation of Kogi State, Nigeria. *World Journal of Biology and Medical Sciences*, 3(1), 82 - 92.
- [8] Agwu COC. (1997). Modern pollen rain in Nsukka: An indicator of the vegetation of Nsukka Plateau. *Wurzbürger Geographische Arbeiten*, 92, 97 -115.
- [9] Agwu COC. (2001). A Study of Niger Delta environment through air-borne palynomorphs, Port-Harcourt, Nigeria. *Palaeoecology of Africa*, 27, 191- 205.
- [10] Germeraad JH, Hoppin CA and Muller J. (1968). Palynology of Tertiary sediments from tropical areas. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology*, 6, 189-348.
- [11] Traverse A. (1988). *Palaeopalynology*. Boston Unwin Hyman Press, London. 227 - 442.
- [12] Ige OE. (2003). The Late Tertiary Environments of the Niger Delta, Nigeria, as indicated by Pollen Analysis. PhD Thesis, Department of Botany and Microbiology, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. 32 - 240.
- [13] Rymer L. (1978). The use of uniformitarianism and analogy in palaeoecology, particularly pollen analysis. In: Walker, D. and Guppy, J.C. (Eds.). *Biology and Quaternary environments*, Australian Academy of Sciences. Canberra. 7-138.
- [14] Birks HJB and Birks HH. (1980). *Quaternary Palaeoecology*. Edward Arnould. London. 117-139.
- [15] Wenner CG. (1947). Pollen diagram from Labrador. *Geology Annals*, 29 (3/4), 374.
- [16] Martin PS and Gray J. (1962). Pollen analysis and the Cenozoic. *Science*, 137, 103-111.
- [17] Bent AM and Wright HEJ. (1963). Pollen analysis of surface materials and lake sediments from the Chuska mountains, New Mexico. *Geological Society of American Bulletin*, 74, 491-500.
- [18] Ogden JG. (1964). Problems in vegetational interpretation of surface pollen spectra from Eastern North America. *AAAS Bulletin*, 87- 128.
- [19] McAndrews JH. (1966). Post glacial history of Praire, Savanna and Forest in Northwestern Minnesota. *Torrey Botanical Club Memograph*, 22 (2), 67-72.

- [20] Nnamani CV and Agwu COC. (2008). Index of the phytoecological indicator species in five honey samples from Ebonyi State of Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Botany*, 21(1), 129-135.
- [21] Patton MQ. (1990). *Quantitative evaluation and research methods*, Second edition. Sage Publications, Newbury Park, CA, 1- 523.
- [22] Tauber H. (1974). A static non-overload pollen collector. *New Phytology*, 73, 359 -369.
- [23] Tauber H. (1977). Investigations of aerial pollen transport in a forested area. *Dansk Botanisk Arkiv*, 32(1), 1 - 121.
- [24] Pardoe HS, Giesecke T, van der Knaap WO, Svitavaska-Svobodova H, Kvavadze EV, Panajiotiotidis S, Gerasimidis A, Pidek IA, Zimney M, Swieta-Musznicka J, Latalowa M, Noryskiewicz AM, Bozilova E, Tonkov S, Filipova-Marinova MV, van Leeuwen JFN and Kalnipa L. (2010). Comparing pollen spectra from modified Tauber traps and moss samples: example from a selection of woodlands across Europe. *Vegetational History and Archaeobotany*, 19, 271 - 283.
- [25] Giesecke T, Fontana SL, van der Knaap WO, Pardoe HS and Pidek IA. (2010). From early pollen trapping experiments to the pollen monitoring programme. *Vegetational History and Archaeobotany*, 19, 247-258.
- [26] Erdtman G. (1969). *Handbook of Palynology*. Muntisguard, Copenhagen, 280 - 285.
- [27] Agwu COC and Akanbi TO. (1985). A palynological study of honey from four vegetation zones of Nigeria. *Pollen et Spores*, 27, 335-348.
- [28] Bonnefille R and Riollet G (1980). *Pollen des savanna d’Afrique orientale*. Anatole Press, Paris, France, 1- 140.
- [29] Sowunmi MA. (1995). Pollen of Nigerian plants II. *Grana*, 34, 120 -141.
- [30] Shubharani R, Roopa P and Sivaram V. (2013). Pollen morphology of selected bee forage plants. *Global Journal of Bio-Science and Biotechnology*, 2(1), 82 – 90.
- [31] White F. (1983). *The Vegetation of Africa*. UNESCO, Paris.
- [32] Onyekwelu SSC and Okafor JC. (1979). Ordination of a savanna woodland in Nigeria using woody and herbaceous species. *Vegetation*, 40(2), 95-100.
- [33] Agwu COC, Njokuocha RC and Mezue O. (2004). The study of airborne pollen and spores circulating at “head level” in Nsukka environment. *Bio-Research*, 2(2), 7 -14.
- [34] Njokuocha RC. (2006). Airborne pollen grains in Nsukka, Nigeria. *Grana*, 45, 73-80.
- [35] Njokuocha RC and Ukeje HO. (2006). The study of airborne pollen precipitation in the University of Nigeria (Nsukka) Botanic Garden. *Bio-Research*, 4(2), 88 - 93.
- [36] Njokuocha RC and Nnamani CV. (2009). Palynological analysis of seven samples of honey from the rainforest-savanna vegetation of east-middle belts of Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Botany*, 22(1), 189-202.
- [37] Njokuocha RC and Ezenwajiaku TE. (2010). Airborne pollen flora in Aguata Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Botany*, 23(2), 211 - 224.
- [38] Essien BC and Agwu COC. (2013). Aeropalynological study of Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria. *Standard Scientific Research Essays*, 1(13), 347-351.
- [39] Essien BC. (2014). A comparative analytical study of airborne pollen grains, spores and other palynomorphs within Grimard Catholic hospital, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria. *Scholarly Journal of Scientific Research and Essay*, 3(5), 56 - 60.
- [40] Essien BC and Aina DO. (2014). The role of airborne pollen grains of some angiosperms and fungal spores in allergic and pathogenic infections in Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advances in Medical Sciences and Biotechnology*, 2(3), 23-28.
- [41] Adeonipekun PA, Agbalaya AE and Adeniyi TA. (2016). Aeropalynology of Ayetoro-Itele, Ota, South-West Nigeria: a preliminary study. In: Alabi R and Adeonipekun PA (Eds), *Human Palaeoecology in Africa: Essays in Honour of M. Adebisi Sowunmi*. University of Ibadan Press, Ibadan, Nigeria, 130 -153.
- [42] Adeniyi TA, Adeonipekun PA and Olowokedujo JD. (2018a). Comparative study of aeropollen and pollinosis cases. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 190, 562-572.

- [43] Bonnefille R, Buchet G, Friis G, Kelbessa E and Mohammed U. (1993). Modern pollen rain on altitudinal range of forests and woodlands in South-West Ethiopia. *Opera Botanica*, 121, 71-84.
- [44] Elenga H, Nammur de C, Vincens A, Roux M and Schwartz D. (2000). Use of plots to define pollen-vegetation relationship in densely forested ecosystems of Tropical Africa. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology*, 112, 76-96.
- [45] Vincens A, Dubois MA, Guillet B, Achoundong G, Buchet G, Kamgang Kabeyene Bayala, V., de Namur C and Riera B. (2000). Pollen rain-vegetation relationships along a forest-savanna transect in southeastern Cameroon. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology*, 110, 191-208.

How to cite this article

Essien BC Idachaba SO and Okai EE. (2019). Index of the phytoecological indicator species in the prevalent airborne pollen types in Akoko environment, Ondo State, Nigeria. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 8(3), 23-41.
